

Indoor environment and energy performance of kindergartens with different thermal design standards

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Abstract: *In the last decades much research and implementation efforts have been invested in improving the thermal standard of buildings. Most of such efforts were motivated by prospects of improving both the environmental conditions in and energy performance of buildings. It is of great importance that such efforts are accompanied by studies that address not just the projected but also the actual performance of buildings. In this context, the present contribution describes a case study of two kindergartens. The purpose of the study was to compare the thermal behavior of a kindergarten built to the Passivhaus standard with one built to default Austrian building regulations. Indoor environmental parameters, such as temperature and relative humidity, along with carbon dioxide levels were monitored and questionnaires were distributed to obtain the subjective evaluations of the occupants. Moreover, actual energy use information was obtained.*

Keywords: *energy, comfort, kindergarten, thermal performance*

1. MOTIVATION AND BACKGROUND

Buildings are responsible for a large fraction of global energy use [1]. Buildings' energy use depends on the design and operation of environmental control systems necessary for the provision of thermal and visual comfort. Indoor environmental conditions affect the health, productivity, and comfort of the inhabitants. Good indoor environmental quality is believed to improve occupants' working and learning performance and reduce absenteeism. It has been suggested, that if occupants find indoor environmental conditions uncomfortable, they may react by trying to restore preferable conditions in energetically inefficient ways [2].

In this context, the present paper reports on a comparative study of two kindergartens in Vienna, Austria. The primary purpose of the study was to see if the performance of a kindergarten built to the Passivhaus standard (PHKG) shows improvements in thermal comfort and energy use when compared to one built to the less stringent default Austrian building regulations (SKG). Toward this end, indoor environmental parameters such as temperature and relative humidity, along with carbon dioxide levels were measured. Furthermore, questionnaires were used to obtain information regarding occupants' subjective comfort perception. Measurement results were interpreted in the context of Passivhaus design criteria, Austrian standards, and questionnaire responses. Energy use data was obtained in terms of electricity and heating energy bills.

2. APPROACH

Two kindergartens were selected for the research. One (PHKG) is built to the Passivhaus standard, the other (SKG) to the applicable Austrian building regulations of the year 2000. Table 1 summarizes, for the main building components of the two kindergartens, the thermal properties in terms of U-values.

Table 1: U-Values (in $W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$) of selected building components of the two kindergartens [3,4,5]

Building Element	PHKG	SKG
Roof	0.10	0.20
Exterior wall	0.13	0.38
Floor slab	0.18	-
Slab on grade	-	0.38
Basement floor slab	-	0.38
Window	0.85	1.60
South façade (glazed)	0.90	-

Building Systems

In PHKG heating is primarily supplied by the compact mechanical ventilation system with high efficiency heat recovery. The incoming fresh air is preheated using ground heat. The design air supply rate is 30 liters per person per hour to maintain carbon dioxide levels below 1000 ppm for a population of 165 people [3]. The classrooms have supplemental hydronic heating (radiant floors). The building is equipped with hot water solar collectors located on the south facade (83 m^2), which support space heating and domestic hot water supply.

Fig. 1 shows the collectors on the south facade as a black band above the classroom windows. A 3800 liter hot water storage tank (centrally placed in the kindergarten atrium) is connected to the solar panels.

Fig. 1: South façade of the PHKG [6]

In contrast, the SKG uses district heating from the City of Vienna for room heating and hot water. Heating is provided via a hydronic radiant floor system. Ventilation is provided via natural means (window operation).

Indoor environmental measurements covered air temperature, relative humidity, and carbon dioxide levels. In each kindergarten, 10 data loggers for temperature and relative humidity as well as one carbon dioxide sensor were located. Measurements were

performed over a period of 23 weeks (from December 16th, 2008 to May 15th, 2009). In addition to measurements, questionnaires were distributed in both kindergartens to obtain subjective (retrospective) assessments of kindergarten teachers and their assistants on the indoor conditions (27 participants in PHKG and 20 in SKG).

To obtain information concerning actual energy use, electricity and heating energy use bills were obtained for both kindergartens (for the year 2008).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study are illustrated below in a series of histograms, cumulative distributions, and psychrometric charts of temperature, relative humidity, and carbon dioxide for occupancy hours during the study period. Results pertain to classrooms (grouped together for each kindergarten) as well as secondary rooms (staff room, atrium, kitchen, children’s toilet, PHKG corridor, and SKG multipurpose room).

3.1 Temperature

In the following figures, the temperature ranges of the five classrooms in each kindergarten are combined. Thereby, the overall temperature range with upper and lower standard limits are shown (19°C to 21°C for winter, and 22.5°C to 24.5°C in summer, see [7]). Fig. 2 illustrates the frequency distribution of temperatures occurring in the occupied classrooms for the six-month study period. Fig. 3 shows the same information in terms of a cumulative frequency distribution. Temperature values for other kindergarten spaces are shown in Fig. 4 to Fig. 7.

Fig. 2: Frequency distribution of temperatures in the occupied classrooms

Fig. 3: Cumulative frequency distribution of temperatures in the occupied classrooms

Fig. 4: Frequency distribution of indoor air temperature in PHKG (secondary rooms temperature)

Fig. 5: Cumulative frequency distribution of indoor air temperature in PHKG (secondary rooms temperature)

Fig. 6: Frequency distribution of indoor air temperature in SKG (secondary rooms temperature)

Fig. 7: Cumulative frequency distribution of indoor air temperature in SKG (secondary rooms temperature)

The temperatures in SKG classrooms are approximately 1 K lower than those in PHKG. PHKG children’s toilet displays high temperatures (Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). Kitchen temperatures are also higher, probably due in part, to cooking and baking activities. The multipurpose room in the SKG also shows high temperatures (Fig. 7). In general, the temperatures observed in the secondary rooms of both kindergartens are often close to or above the upper temperature limit defined by the standards (4 K higher in PHKG, 3 K in SKG). Temperatures in occupied individual classrooms for the observation period are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. Overall, the temperature distributions are rather similar. However, temperature variance is somewhat higher amongst the PHKG classrooms.

Fig. 8: Temperature box plot of individual classrooms during occupied hours in the PHKG for the study period

Fig. 9: Temperature box plot of individual classrooms during occupied hours in the SKG for the study period

3.2 Relative Humidity

Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 illustrate the frequency of indoor humidity levels occurring in the 10 classrooms for the observation period. The recommended humidity range is between 30% and 70% in the European Standard [8]. PHKG humidity levels are within this range over 79% of the entire observation period. SKG humidity levels remain 92% of the time within this range. SKG rooms show higher humidity levels. Assuming a narrower range for desirable relative humidity, namely between 40% and 60% [9], the PHKG display humidity levels lower than the recommended values for 35% of the period, whereas the SKG is below the lower humidity limit only 8% of the time. These results are consistent with general experiences with most Passivhaus standard buildings, in which the controlled ventilation system can lead to rather low relative humidity values (particularly in winter). Fig. 12 to Fig. 15 show the indoor humidity levels in the secondary rooms of the kindergartens. Concerning PHKG, the high humidity level in the kitchen may be due to moisture production caused by cooking, baking, and washing. Lower humidity levels in the PHKG children's toilet are a consequence of higher temperatures in this space (Fig. 12).

Fig. 10: Frequency distribution of indoor relative humidity (classrooms)

Fig. 11: Cumulative frequency distribution of indoor relative humidity (classrooms)

Fig. 12: Frequency distribution of indoor relative humidity (PHKG, secondary rooms)

Fig. 13: Cumulative frequency distribution of humidity (PHKG, secondary rooms)

Fig. 14: Frequency distribution of indoor relative humidity (SKG, secondary rooms)

Fig. 15: Cumulative frequency distribution of humidity (SKG, secondary rooms)

3.3 Psychrometric Analysis

Fig. 16 to Fig. 21 illustrate the indoor conditions in the classrooms of the two kindergartens as psychrometric charts for the months of December, March, and May (occupied hours). Thereby, the recommended comfort boundaries are included (see Sections 3.1 and 3.2). These diagrams highlight the large fraction of intervals outside the recommended boundaries (especially in case of PHKG). Table 2 summarizes, for the entire monitoring period, the monthly percentage of time, where indoor conditions were within the recommended boundaries. The higher percentages for SKG during April and May could be attributed to higher window operation frequency. As will be seen in the questionnaire responses in Section 0, the kindergartens' staff (particularly SKG) also found temperatures generally be too high. Therefore, there is agreement between the recorded temperatures and user perceptions.

Fig. 16: PHKG classroom conditions (December)

Fig. 17: SKG classroom conditions (December)

Fig. 18: PHKG classroom conditions (March)

Fig. 19: SKG classroom conditions (March)

Fig. 20: PHKG classroom conditions (May)

Fig. 21: SKG classroom conditions (May)

Table 2: Percentage of occupied hours with indoor conditions meeting applicable thermal standards [7,8].

Month	PHKG [%]	SKG [%]
December	9.1	11.8
January	5.1	8.4
February	0.8	0.8
March	0.0	1.0
April	10.0	42.3
May	7.6	45.7

3.4 Carbon dioxide concentration

One indicator of indoor air quality is carbon dioxide concentration. The indoor concentration should be no more than 500 ppm over outdoor carbon dioxide levels in order to meet Category II requirements [7]. The ventilation system in the PHKG is designed to keep carbon dioxide levels below 1000 ppm for a population of 165 people [3]. Thus, the upper limit for the purpose of this study is set at 1000 ppm.

Fig. 22 and Fig. 23 show the overall measured carbon dioxide concentration levels in both kindergartens (classrooms) for the study period during the occupied hours. For comparison purposes, Fig. 24 and Fig. 25 show concentration levels during the unoccupied periods. In the occupied hours, PHKG remains longer under 1000 ppm CO₂ concentration (7%), indicating a slightly better indoor air quality. This is possibly due to the constant air exchange maintained by the ventilation system. However, CO₂ concentrations are above the 1000 ppm benchmark for a large portion of the occupied period in both kindergartens (32% in PHKG, 39% in SKG). These results warrant two observations. First, the monitored high CO₂ concentration levels are consistent with other studies of indoor air quality in classrooms [10]. Classrooms also have one of the highest occurring densities of all occupancy types. Second, the actual occupancy density of a building in use may differ from the original design assumptions. For example, in the present case, the initial occupancy density assumption for PHKG was 165. The actual is, however, closer to 210.

Fig. 22: Frequency distribution of CO₂ (occupied classrooms)

Fig. 23: Cumulative frequency distribution of CO₂ (occupied classrooms)

Fig. 24: Frequency distribution of CO₂ (unoccupied classrooms)

Fig. 25: Frequency distribution of CO₂ (unoccupied classrooms)

The comparison of the cumulative distributions of the occupied and unoccupied classrooms (Figures 21 and 23) clearly shows the occupancy influence. The lower carbon dioxide levels in PHKG may be attributed to the constant air circulation due to the ventilation system. In the warmer months (April and May) the IAQ shows improvement (in both kindergartens), given a higher frequency of natural ventilation usage. This may be illustrated via Figures 26 and 27, which show time-dependent carbon dioxide concentrations for two weeks in winter and late spring respectively.

Fig. 26: Carbon dioxide levels (occupied classrooms, from January 25th to 31st, 2008)

Fig. 27: Carbon dioxide levels) occupied classrooms, from May 3rd to 10th, 2008)

3.5 Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) and Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied (PPD)

Figures 28 and 29 show the distribution of calculated PMV values (occupied classrooms) in the two kindergartens over the observation period [11]. The PMV values were calculated based on the measurements of temperature and relative humidity. Note that for the purpose of obtaining PMV values, the mean radiant temperature was assumed to be equal to the (measured values of) indoor air temperature, and the indoor air flow velocity was uniformly assumed to be 0.1 m·s⁻¹. Moreover, the thermal resistance of occupants' clothing was assumed to be 0.5 clo for summer, 0.85 clo for spring/autumn, and 1.0 clo for winter. Activity level was assumed to be 1.4 met. Satisfaction with thermal conditions (as expressed in terms of PMV values) appears to be slightly higher in the SKG classrooms. Moreover, PMV values imply that both kindergartens are likely to be perceived as slightly warm in all classrooms for the majority of time during the period of observation.

Fig. 28: PHKG PMV for the observation period

Fig. 29: SKG PMV for the observation period

3.6 Questionnaire Results

Table 3 shows the results of the survey conducted amongst kindergarten teachers and assistants.

Table 3: Summary of the results of user survey in the two kindergartens.

		PHKG [%]	SKG [%]
User estimate of the time (each day) windows are open (Summer)	30 minutes or less	11.1	0
	About 1 hour	7.4	0
	3 hours and more	81.5	100
User estimate of the time (each day) windows are open (Winter)	30 minutes or less	38.5	17.6
	About 1 hour	46.2	64.7
	3 hours and more	15.4	17.7
Users' assessment of indoor air quality	Good	14.8	36.8
	Neutral	40.7	15.8
	Poor	44.4	47.4
Users' satisfaction with ventilation possibilities	Satisfied	11.2	40
	Neutral	37	30
	Dissatisfied	51.8	30
Users' assessment of indoor temperature (Winter)	Cold	33.3	0
	Cool	14.8	15
	Neutral	11.1	10
	Warm	29.6	65
	Hot	11.1	10
Users' assessment of indoor relative humidity (Winter)	Humid	3.7	0
	Neutral	22.2	36.8
	Dry	74.1	63.2

The questionnaire results must be viewed with caution, given the one-time and "retrospective" mode of inquiry. Taken at face value, they appear to suggest the following: Both kindergartens are perceived as rather dry (particularly PHKG). Moreover, SKG is perceived to be warmer than PHKG, despite the comparatively lower indoor air temperatures. The wider distribution of perceived temperatures in PHKG is consistent with the higher variance of measured temperatures in this kindergarten's classrooms. Dissatisfaction with ventilation possibilities is high, particularly in PHKG. Likewise, indoor air quality does not receive high marks in both kindergartens. The slightly better

evaluation of indoor air quality in SKG may be due to higher natural ventilation frequency (particularly in summer).

3.7 Energy Analysis

Detailed monitoring of energy use could not be conducted in the two kindergartens. However, a global comparison of the energy performance of the two kindergartens can be made for the year 2008 based on available energy bills. Accordingly, Fig. 30 illustrates the total annual area-specific energy use for heating/hot water and electricity. Note that the exact quantity of thermal energy production in PHKG via the aforementioned solar collectors is not known and hence is not deduced from the data shown in Fig. 30. As it stands (i.e., with the inclusion of free heating via solar collectors), the thermal energy use by PHKG for heating and hot water is less than half of the energy used by SKG. Electrical energy use is, however, somewhat higher in the case of PHKG (see also Fig. 31, with the monthly break down of the electrical energy use in both kindergartens). This is in all likelihood due to the additional energy required for the ventilation system and the circulation pumps of the solar panels.

Fig. 30: Total annual energy use.

Fig. 31: Monthly break down of the electrical energy use in both kindergartens

4. CONCLUSION

PHKG can be said to have a better energy performance than SKG: A somewhat higher electrical energy use is compensated by a significantly lower thermal energy use. Energy use for heating could be further reduced in both kindergartens, given the prevailing high temperatures. Indoor air quality (expressed in terms of CO₂ concentration) appears to be slightly better in PHKG. However, CO₂ concentration levels are rather high in both kindergartens, implying a suboptimal sizing and/or operation of the ventilation systems. Overall, our study implies that recent improvements in buildings' thermal standards have indeed resulted in a higher level of energy efficiency. Improvements in indoor climate, however, do not seem to have occurred to a commensurate extent. Remaining challenges pertain thus to issues such as optimal systems operation, harmonization of natural and controlled ventilation regimes, as well as more user-responsive building systems controls and interfaces.

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